

THE DIFFERENT ASPECTS OF POLYSEMY OF SOME ITS RELATED EVENTS

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ko'pma'nolilikning yuzaga kelishi, ko'pma'nolilikning birma'nolilik hamda ma'no kengayishi va torayishi kabi hodisalardan farqli jihatlari yoritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ko'p ma'nolilik, ko'chma ma'no, monosemantik leksema, shakl va mazmun, ma'no kengayishi, ma'no torayishi.

Abstract. This article describes the occurrence of polysemy, the different aspects of polysemy from such phenomena as ambiguity and expansion and contraction of meaning.

Key words: polysemy, figurative meaning, monosemantic lexeme, form and content, expansion of meaning, narrowing of meaning.

INTRODUCTION

Polysemy has attracted the attention of scientists since ancient times. Mirtojiev said that this phenomenon was studied by Chinese and Indian scientists before our era, and by the Greeks at the beginning of our era, from our ancestors to this event M. Kashgari, Zamakhshari, A. Navoi, among our ancestors, also wrote that they expressed their views. (2, p. 3). The multi-meaning of the word makes it possible to memorize a small amount of words, to express a relatively large amount of meaning and to make maximum use of understanding. This makes it easier to learn other languages. Ambiguity is a linguistic phenomenon that serves to express speech figuratively and impressively. A word with many meanings, a lexeme is a linguistic unit. In the text, the word realizes one of its meanings. Changes in the life of the society, of course, are reflected in the language. This is clearly shown by the new creations in our vocabulary, or the borrowed words of the following years. As the vocabulary of the language changes as a result of the development of the society, the words in the language are updated and changed semantically. So, words in the language change and update lexically and semantically, and as a result of that semantic development, the phenomenon of ambiguity occurs. Ambiguous words are created as a result of the imposition of a new meaning on a previously existing word due to the attempt to express unlimited concepts and ideas from limited units of language. A word that has two or more meanings is considered a polysemous word, while words that express only one meaning in the language are monosemantic (one-semantic) words. Russian linguist L.A. Novikov recognizes three types of the relationship between a sign and its meaning, which creates ambiguity. The first type of relationship between a sign and its meaning is associated with monosemy... In this case, there is a correlation between the sign and its meaning. The second type, which paves the way for polysemy a) polysemantic units are close to monosemantic units, and the distance between polysemantic units is weak and smaller; b) in polysemy, the distance between the sign and its meanings is significant and strong. If in the first type the sign and its meaning are almost consistent, in the second type the connection between them is free. It has more semantic units than a sign, and they can be expressed more widely in the scope of other synonymous signs. The next type of relationship between a sign and its meaning is homonymy, which is characterized by the semantic variation of a polysemous unit, and the

connection between semantic units ceases. So, polysemy is a linguistic semantic category between the extremes of monosemy and homonymy (3, P.193). In fact, in monosemantic words, form and content are proportional, while in polysemantic words, form and content are disproportional. New words (neologisms) introduced into the language initially express one meaning, but later they can express several meanings. For example, the word virus initially means a microorganism that reproduces only in living cells and causes infectious diseases in humans and plants. (4, 1- volume P. 462) If it means, then it also means the name of a tool that damages programs and data in technical devices such as computers, telephones, that is, ambiguity has arisen. Ambiguity is a product of language development. It should be noted here that any monosemantic lexemes can become polysemantic lexemes, that is, even monosemantic lexemes have the possibility of polysemanticity. A single-meaning lexeme can always create a new meaning, and polysemantic words can become homonyms. The development of monosemantic lexemes can create polysemy, as well as the development of polysemantic words can create homonymous lexemes. Monosemantic lexeme - polysemantic lexeme - homonymous lexeme. The linguistic essence of polysemy is explained by the asymmetry of sign and meaning, which do not completely cover each other. The difference between polysemy and the phenomenon of expansion and contraction of lexical meaning. In the course of the historical development of the language, the meanings of the words also change in connection with the changes in the vocabulary. Although some words do not change in form, they change in meaning. Words with several meanings can be used in one sense, and vice versa, words with one meaning can be used in several meanings, that is, narrowing and expanding the meaning of words. For example, in the past, the word millet meant grain in general, and the word deer meant all wild animals, but now millet means a kind of grain, deer a kind of wild animal.

The phenomena of polysemy and broadening and narrowing of meaning are different. M. Mirtojiyev explains these two phenomena as follows: "The occurrence of polysemy is the formation of more than one lexical meaning. An extension of meaning is only an internal change of meaning. That is, they are different language phenomena. In the expansion of the meaning, the scope of the concept it means expands, and no new lexical meaning is formed in it. The expanded lexical meaning expresses the same expression as before, only the amount or size of the referent that that lexical meaning signifies increases" (1, P. 168). In the book of Semasiology, M. Hakimova states that the result of the change of lexical meaning is twofold, i.e. 1) the increase in the number of meanings in the semantic structure of a lexeme leads to polysemy, and later to homonymy; 2) It notes the change in the meaning of the lexeme, in which the meaning expands or shrinks without creating a new meaning (5, p. 67). It is clear from the above considerations that the phenomena of ambiguity and meaning expansion and narrowing are different from each other. So, in polysemy, one meaning grows out of another meaning that depends on it. For example, a flower grew, meaning grew. In expansion and contraction of meaning, the signified meaning expands (increases) or narrows (decreases) without creating new meaning. For example, if the word village means "a place where you live in winter", it means a place where people live, not a city.

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